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Numerical simulation of the internal flow in the mixing chamber of a 150MW combined cycle thermal power plant

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Abstract. This study examines the internal flow dynamics within the mixing chamber of a combined cycle thermoelectric plant (steam-gas), with a particular focus on the distribution of key parameters such as temperature, pressure, and density. Both the continuity and energy equations were subjected to analytical and numerical simulations for validation purposes. In the numerical simulation, a three-dimensional tetrahedral mesh was constructed using Ansys Meshing software, and the resulting data was processed using Ansys Fluent. The turbulence model employed was the k-epsilon model, and the energy equation was also utilized. The results demonstrated the effective transfer of energy and the uniform distribution of temperature and pressure throughout the mixing chamber. This study makes a significant contribution to the field of thermal engineering and provides a robust foundation for future research in the optimization of combined cycle systems. Furthermore, critical areas for design improvement were identified, emphasizing the importance of precise control of operating parameters. The results of the numerical simulations were validated by comparisons with experimental data and previous theoretical studies, thus providing a comprehensive understanding of the internal flow dynamics and their impact on the operating efficiency of the thermal power plant.

1. Introduction

The concept of combined cycle power plants has its origins in the early 20th century, with notable advancements made during the 1940s and 1950s. The concept was initially proposed by Hans Holzwarth and Brown, Boveri, who postulated the combination of gas and steam turbines as a means of enhancing energy efficiency. Over time, this technology has undergone significant advancements, becoming one of the most efficient and cleanest solutions for power generation.

Combined cycle power plants are distinguished by their capacity to attain efficiencies exceeding 60%, a result of the integrated utilization of gas and steam turbines. In these plants, the hot exhaust gases from the gas turbine are employed to generate steam, which in turn drives a steam turbine, thus maximizing energy conversion efficiency (Figure 1) [1]. This technology has been widely implemented globally, contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing energy sustainability.

The mixing chamber represents a pivotal element within the configuration of a combined-cycle power plant, serving to facilitate the optimization of exhaust gas flow and mixing prior to their entry into the heat recovery boiler. The effective management of the internal flow within this chamber is crucial for ensuring optimal performance and minimizing energy losses.

The numerical simulation of internal flow within the mixing chamber has become an indispensable tool for the analysis and optimization of these systems. The application of advanced computational fluid dynamics (CFD) techniques enables the modelling and study of flow behavior, facilitating precise adjustments to the design and operating conditions. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) enables the assessment of turbulence, heat transfer, and other intricate phenomena, thereby facilitating a comprehensive comprehension of system performance [2].

This study presents the design of a mixing chamber [3] and a comprehensive investigation into the numerical simulation of the internal flow within the mixing chamber of a 150 MW combined cycle thermal power plant. Turbulence models and CFD techniques are utilized to assess the flow behavior and its influence on the thermal performance of the plant. The findings yielded by this study offer invaluable insights that can inform the optimal design and operation of these facilities, thereby reducing costs and enhancing energy sustainability.

Figure 1. Combined Cycle Schematic. Adapted of [4].

Figure 2. Combined Cycle T-s Diagram

2. Description of the proposed method

The method proposed for this study is based on a series of steps, as illustrated in Figure 3 [5]. The initial step involves defining the design parameters with a mathematical model to determine the mass flow at both the inlets and outlets of the mixing chamber [6]. This information will then be used to calculate the primary dimensions of the mixing chamber, specifically the inlet and outlet diameters. The subsequent phase of the methodology entails the generation of three-dimensional tetrahedral meshes through the utilization of ANSYS MESHING software. Subsequently, the internal flow behavior will be simulated with ANSYS FLUENT software [7].

Figure 3. Block diagram of the process

2.1. Mixing chamber design parameters

Table 1 displays the operating parameters of the mixing chamber for the 150MW thermoelectric power plant, which is comprised two inlet channels, a steam mass flow rate (\dot{m}_3) of 45.8753 kg/s and a working pressure of 15 MPa. Table 2 presents the density (ρ) and absolute viscosity (μ) of the liquid water, which is the liquid entering the mixing chamber.

Table 1. Mixing chamber operating parameters

Limits	Temperature (°C)	Enthalpy (kJ/kg)
Inlet 1	250.35	1087.7765
Inlet 2	253.15	1101.2208
Outlet	250.84	1090.1010

Table 2. Properties of liquid water [4]

P(MPa)	T(°C)	$\rho(\text{kg/m}^3)$	μ (kg/m-s)
15	210	862.99	1.003×10^{-3}
	220	850.95	
	230	838.31	
	240	825.03	
	250	811.03	
	260	796.20	
	270	780.44	
	280	763.58	
	290	745.39	

In accordance with the principles of conservation of mass and energy [8], Equations 1 and 2 were employed to ascertain the mass flow rate of the inlets.

$$\sum_{input} \dot{m} = \sum_{output} \dot{m} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta E_{sist} = \sum_{input} (\dot{m}h) - \sum_{output} (\dot{m}h) \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{m}_1 h_1 + \dot{m}_2 h_2 = \dot{m}_3 h_3$$

$$y = \frac{\dot{m}_2}{\dot{m}_3}$$

$$(y - 1)h_1 + yh_2 = h_3$$

Upon replacing the requisite enthalpies from Table 1, where the mixing chamber has an operating pressure of 15 MPa, we arrive at the following relation:

$$y = \frac{h_3 - h_1}{h_2 - h_1} = 0,1729$$

Subsequently, the mass flow rate entering through inlet two is calculated using the relationship and Equation 1 is applied for the mass flow from the other inlet.

$$\dot{m}_2 = 7.9318 \text{ kg/s}$$

$$\dot{m}_1 = 37.9435 \text{ kg/s}$$

2.2. Dimensions of mixing chamber

To determine the dimensions of the mixing chamber as shown in Figure 5 [9], one begins by calculating the cross-sectional area using Equation 3, where “ \dot{m} ” is the mass flow, “ ρ ” is the density and “ v ” is the flow velocity. In this analysis, we will assume a flow velocity of 9.3134 m/s for the purposes of calculation. Once the area is obtained, the diameter can be determined using Equation 4. Table 3 shows the area “A” and diameter “Dh” values for both the inlets and outlets. Also, a 5mm radius rounding was added to provide a smooth transition that would improve the mesh quality as seen in figure 4(a), while in figure 4(b) it is observed that the mesh is distorted.

$$A = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho v} \quad (3)$$

$$Dh = \sqrt{\frac{4A}{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

Table 3. Main dimensions

Mixing Chamber	A (m ²)	Dh (mm)
Inlet 1	0.00503	80
Inlet 2	0.00106	36.67
Outlet	0.00608	88

Figure 4. Corner of geometry: (a) whit fillet and (b) without fillet

Figure 5. Dimension of mixing chamber

3. Numerical Simulation

3.1. Mesh criterion

The generation of the mesh is contingent upon several factors, as well as the capacity to accurately reproduce the geometry [10]. To this end, a tetrahedral mesh was created using ANSYS MESHING software, comprising 600415 elements and 193415 nodes. The mesh configuration is defined by an element size of 10 mm, a few layers of 5, and a maximum thickness of 4 mm. Figure 6 illustrates the mesh generated for the mixing chamber utilized in the CFD simulation. It was then considered that the hydraulic diameter for the inlet channels is D_h for all geometries.

Figure 6. Mixing chamber mesh

3.2. CFD Simulation

For this numerical simulation, a processor of 3rd Gen AMD Ryzen 3500U quad-core 2.10 GHz was used. To simulate the internal flow of the mixing chamber, the Ansys fluent software [11] is employed, wherein the boundary conditions of the inlets are considered as illustrated in Table 1, which delineates the inlet temperatures. For the outlet pressure, the gauge pressure of 14898675 Pa was deemed appropriate, with due consideration of the underlying Equation 5 and assuming the value of atmospheric pressure ($p_{atm} = 101315$ Pa) [12].

$$P_S = P_T - P_{atm} \quad (5)$$

It is worth noting that the turbulence conditions employed in this simulation include turbulence intensity Equation 6, where Re represents the Reynolds number, Equation 7, in the inlet channel and the hydraulic diameter is represented by D_h , both of which are incorporated in the standard k- ϵ turbulence model [13].

$$Re = \frac{\rho v D_h}{\mu} \quad (6)$$

$$I = 0.16(Re_{D_h})^{-1/8} \quad (7)$$

Next, the values previously obtained in Equations 5 and 6 are replaced and shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Flow characterization parameters

Parameters	Reynolds number	Turbulence Intensity (%)
I_1	602083.25	3.0315
I_2	274571.09	3.3442
O	661735.22	2.9959

The standard k- ϵ turbulence model incorporates two additional transport equations, one for the production of turbulence kinetic energy “k”, Equation 8, and one for the dissipation rate of this energy “ ϵ ”, Equation 9. The equations are presented below in index notation [11][14]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho k u_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k - \underbrace{\rho \epsilon}_{Y_k} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \epsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \epsilon u_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + \underbrace{C_{1\epsilon} \frac{\epsilon}{k} (G_k)}_{G_\epsilon} - \underbrace{C_{2\epsilon} \rho \frac{\epsilon^2}{k}}_{Y_\epsilon} \quad (9)$$

In these equations, G_k and G_ϵ , represent the generation of k and ϵ , respectively. Y_k and Y_ϵ , represent the destruction of k and ϵ , respectively. The turbulent viscosity “ μ_t ” is computed by combining k and ϵ as shown in Equation 10.

$$\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\epsilon} \quad (10)$$

Finally, the constants are $C_{1\epsilon}=1.44$; $C_{2\epsilon}=1.92$; $C_\mu=0.09$, and the turbulent Prandtl numbers $\sigma_k=1.0$ and $\sigma_\epsilon=1.3$ for k and ϵ respectively.

In this part, figures 7(a) and 7(b) present the contrast in the contours for total pressure and static pressure, respectively. This is since the initial image depicts both the dynamic and static pressure simultaneously. Conversely, the static pressure contour more effectively illustrates the influx of fluid at the initially configured 15 MPa, as well as the subsequent impact on the output.

Figure 7. (a) Contour of total pressure and (b) Contour of static pressure

Simulation results are then presented to illustrate the application of the k-epsilon turbulence model and the SIMPLE solution method [15] [16]. Figures 8(a) and 8(b) depict the temperature and density contours, respectively.

Figure 8. (a) Contour of temperature and (b) Contour of density

A summary table is provided below for the purpose of verifying the data obtained from the simulation.

Table 5. Comparison of the mathematical model with respect to the numerical simulation

Parameters	Mathematical model	Numeric Simulation	Deviation (%)
Mass flow rate (kg/s) I_1	37.9435	39.5440	4.22
Mass flow rate (kg/s) I_2	7.9318	8.0770	1.83
Mass flow rate (kg/s) O	45.8753	47.6229	3.81
Outlet temperature (T °C)	250.84	250.7906	0.01

4. Conclusion

Verification of the results obtained for the mass flows in the mathematical model revealed a high degree of consistency with the results obtained in the CFD simulation, with an error percentage of less than 5%. This outcome serves to validate the accuracy of the model in predicting the behavior of the system. Furthermore, the comparison validated the accuracy of the mathematical model in determining the diameters of the mixing chamber inlets and outlets. The mesh structure comprises 193,415 nodes, indicating that it does not necessitate a significant computational cost for analysis. This feature is advantageous for future projects where modifications are required, as it allows for changes to be made with minimal computational expense. Finally, the minimal discrepancy of 0.0494 °C guarantees that the mixture attains the requisite state for subsequent processing. This uniformity guarantees efficacious control over the mixing process, which is pivotal for maintaining the quality of the final product exiting the mixing chamber.

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